

Additional file 6. PageMan analysis of coordinated changes of gene functional categories during 2 h, 4 h, 6 h, 12 h or 24 h of deacclimation (DEA) or in non-acclimated (NA) plants of *Arabidopsis thaliana* relative to cold acclimated plants. Normalized gene expression values were subjected to an overrepresentation analysis to identify functional categories that contained significantly more or less regulated genes than expected by chance. Blue color indicates significant enrichment of up- or down-regulated genes, red indicates significant depletion.